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Good practice guide

Use of the digital twin of the calibrated array spectroradiometers

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1. Scope

The NEWSTAND App provides a spectroradiometer data processor with graphical user interface (GUI) that enables the calculation of spectral irradiance from the raw spectrometer output and characterization data and a corresponding measurement uncertainty analysis. This good practice guide describes the implemented models, the functionality of the graphical user interface and how to prepare the input data.

2. General

Accurate conversion of raw spectroradiometer data into radiometric and photometric quantities with associated measurement uncertainties is essential for absolute calibrated measurements but remains challenging in practice. Modern array spectrometers output pixel indices and digital counts that must undergo e.g., pixel to wavelength transfer and spectral responsivity correction provided by radiometric characterisations and calibrations, to obtain physically meaningful quantities such as spectral irradiance or illuminance [CIE 250:2022].

Each processing step applies necessary corrections with its associated measurement uncertainties, including those from detector noise, calibration errors, wavelength inaccuracies, and other systematic effects. Although the mathematical transformations are well established, rigorous and traceable uncertainty propagation across the full processing chain is often inconsistent or neglected. The diversity of array spectroradiometer hardware and software including the entrance optics, calibration procedures, and data formats further complicates reproducible and validated analysis. In many applications, uncertainty estimates are oversimplified or omitted, despite being crucial for instrument comparison, conformity assessment, and quantitative modelling. Existing software tools typically focus on visualization or basic calibration and rarely provide transparent, standardized workflows that maintain a complete uncertainty budget.

To address these limitations, an open-source Python-based implementation that converts raw digital spectroradiometer data into radiometric and photometric quantities with comprehensive Monte Carlo-based uncertainty propagation was developed in the 22IEM05 NEWSTAND project. Within this software, corrections and their measurement uncertainties determined during the characterization of the array spectroradiometers are considered. As a result, spectral and spectrally integrated quantities are obtained in physically meaningful units with full measurement uncertainty, enabling array spectroradiometers to be used as transfer standard instruments in spectroradiometry.

The software provides a graphical user interface for ease of use and visualization of every processing step. Different models can be used for the transfer of raw spectroradiometer output into physical quantities. Each model defines the application and the order of radiometric corrections. Radiometric corrections for dark data, non-linearity, straylight, optical bandwidth, spectral responsivity and pixel number to wavelength transfer are available. Figure 1 shows the visual representation of *Model 3* including the order of the applied corrections and the connection between calibration and measurement chain. While the users can define their own models in the source code, three of them are provided and ready to use. The fourth model will be implemented by the end of the project:

- **Model 1:** Includes the before-mentioned radiometric corrections and models the spectral responsivity (SR) with a best-estimate value and a type A measurement uncertainty without wavelength correlations.
- **Model 2:** Extension of model 1, SR data is provided as a Monte Carlo data set allowing to model wavelength correlations.
- **Model 3:** Similar to model 2 but SR is calculated separately during each Monte Carlo run using the measured raw data of the calibration (“calibration chain”). Due to the usage of two data chains, calibration and measurements are modelled in a consistent manner.
- **Model 4:** Extension of model 3. It adds device-correlations between the calibration and the measurement chain. We consider this model as the most accurate in terms of determination of measurement uncertainties.

All models allow to carry out a full Monte Carlo analysis. As a result, spectral data as well as spectrally integrated data is obtained with its corresponding measurement uncertainty.

Within this good practice guide, we describe the graphical user interface and the settings file of the spectrometer which is to be modelled. The software itself is called NEWSTAND App in the following.

Figure 1. Model 3 as implemented in the analysis software. It implements two data processing chains to fully propagate wavelength correlations of the spectral responsivity.

3. The graphical user interface

All code is written in Python and can be executed directly to start the NEWSTAND App. The code is also compiled into a standalone program (.exe file) for Windows 11. The program can be stored in any directory of the computer. It is recommended to store it somewhere with writing permissions as the software tries to save a settings file in the folder of the executable to save the last opened data.

The graphical user interface is shown in **Figure 2**. The user interface is structured into three sections:

- The left panel defines the user input via the selection of the spectrometer model, the measurement and calibration files. It also contains a list of the different steps and corrections within the calibration and the measurement chain. On the lower-left section, different settings for the Monte Carlo simulation can be defined, the best-estimate (“Run Single Model”) and the Monte Carlo model (“Run Monte Carlo”) can be run and results can be saved to a file.
- The middle panel contains the resulting graphical representation of the results and, when available, the input files are shown.
- On the right panel, log messages provide detailed information on the progress and error messages about missing or not correctly formatted files. This panel is collapsible to allow for an expanded view for the middle plot.

Figure 2. User Interface of the NEWSTAND App.

The NEWSTAND App expects three input files. The modelling of a spectrometer is specified in a spectrometer settings file. Measurement data must include a light data file and a dark data file. The files are selected via the three buttons in the upper left in the sections “Spectrometer” and “Measurement”, see

Figure 2.

Underneath the light/dark-data buttons a label depicts the currently applied model as specified in the spectrometer settings file. A list of the corrections selected for modelling follows, see **Figure 3**. If a file was not found or couldn't be loaded correctly, the background color changes to red. Each item of the list is selectable. Upon selection, the NEWSTAND App changes the central tab to the “Radiometric Object” tab. On the right side of the middle section, a description of the object is given in a text box on the left which displays additional information on the applied model and the required input data. If the model has been run (see next paragraph), the input and output data of the object is shown in the graph as well as the relative change from input to output data due to the applied correction. For x-y data (For example pixel-signal for the light or dark object) the additional “Visualize Input Data” can be selected to inspect the raw input data.

Figure 3. List of the corrections applied in the model.

The list is followed by buttons that execute the model (see **Figure 4**), either in a single run or in a Monte Carlo simulation. The single run button applies the model to get a best estimate which includes all corrections but does not include measurement uncertainties. The main purpose is to check if the input data is valid and the applied corrections work as expected or if just a spectral irradiance without measurement uncertainty is required. After a successful run, the result can be saved with the respective button (“Save Single Run”). The software creates a result file in plain text and an image file with the same name displaying the graph on the results file tab.

Figure 4. Running the model and the Monte Carlo simulation

On the lower-left part settings for the Monte Carlo Simulation can be defined (see **Figure 4**). The Monte Carlo simulation is only enabled after a successful single run. The number of Monte Carlo runs is adjustable. The NEWSTAND App is currently not speed optimized and does not use several cores for the Monte Carlo analysis. Depending on your computer and the radiometric model used, the simulation may take a while when going to number of runs higher than 10000.

Figure 5. The “Radiometric Object” tab shows the transformation by the correction selected in the list.

The settings for the confidence interval are used for plotting of the results and the export via the “save MC result” button. The saving routine exports the Monte Carlo results with respective uncertainties in a “.txt” file and the graph displayed on the Monte Carlo Tab as a “.png” image file.

The middle part of the app is used to plot all the acquired data, either the raw input data or the data generated by the analysis. There are in general 3 tabs. The first “Radiometric Object” tab displays the data transformation by each applied correction step (see **Figure 5**). The relative change resulting from the correction is shown as well.

If raw input data is available, a second tab “Visualize Input Data” is created to display the raw data. The raw input data has to be in x-y data format or in a matrix format. If for example, polynomial coefficients are supplied by the input data, they cannot be shown in this tab. **Figure 6** shows the visualization of a straylight matrix.

Figure 6. The “Visualize Input Data” tab shows a visual representation of the input data of the selected object selected in the list **Figure 3**. A heatmap to represent a straylight matrix is currently displayed.

The “Result” tab displays the result of the Single model run without any uncertainties, see **Figure 7**. The final “Monte Carlo Simulation” tab shows the result of the Monte Carlo analysis, see **Figure 8**. The mean spectral irradiance (best estimate) is shown as well as the last result of the simulation. Additionally, the uncertainty of the x- and y- axis are shown. At each point you can save and clear the currently displayed graph using the corresponding buttons at the bottom. A crosshair is implemented on the Monte Carlo Simulation graph which reads out the current mouse position in the graph. The coordinates are shown below the graph. On a left click, the movement of the crosshair is frozen for a precise readout.

Only for the Monte Carlo Simulation Graph: You can check/uncheck the box at the bottom to show the uncertainty in relative or absolute values.

Figure 7. The result of the Single model run without any uncertainties.

Figure 8. The Monte Carlo Simulation Tab shows the result of the Monte Carlo analysis. The mean spectral irradiance (best estimate) is shown as well as the last result of the simulation. The red graph is the mean spectral irradiance, averaged over all runs. Green shows the uncertainty of the spectral irradiance and blue the uncertainty in wavelength. In the displayed case the wavelength error is extrapolated to an error in spectral irradiance.

4. Input data: General guidelines

In total, the following data needs to be provided:

- Settings file: A settings file, where the model and each processing step (applied correction) is defined.
- Measurement data: Light and dark signal measurement, stored in individual data files.
- Characterization data: Individual input data file for certain radiometric corrections.

4.1. Format of the settings-file

The data processing is defined in a text file using an INI-like configuration format, referred to as settings-file. It defines the overall model, the model used for each processing step (e.g. an applied correction) as well as the corresponding input data for the processing step. The type of input data varies for the different processing steps depending e.g. on the model used to describe the physical effect. It can be in the form of parameters, polynomial coefficients or as data lists.

Please note that if additional input files are required these have to be stored in the same directory as the settings file.

There are several examples provided with the NEWSTAND App that can be used as guidelines for users to create their own files. It is recommended to use one of these examples as a starting point for your data.

General remarks about the settings-file:

- A data file is separated into different sections.
- Each section starts with its name in square brackets.
- In each block different information is stored.
- Each information consists of a key-value pair.
- The settings file uses “key = value” pairs.
- Comments can be added by starting the line with the “#” character.

As an example, a section could look like this:

```
[General]
# In this section the Model is defined which will be used for analysis
# additional data as comment

Model = Newstand3
Spectrometer name = Min3
Serial number = Min3_xxx_xxx
```

4.2. Format of measurement and characterization data

The measurement and characterization data need to be also prepared in text-file format (.txt). The files have to follow a strict formatting style to be readable by the code. It is necessary for the correct readout. Please refer to the provided example data to bring your data in the correct format. A few general remarks here:

- A data file is separated into different blocks.
- Each block starts with its name in square brackets.
- In each block different information is stored.
- Each information consists of a key-value pair.
- For input data, the formatting style “key: → value” or “key: → value → unit” is used, i.e. a keyword followed by a colon and a tab stop (tabs are shown with a → symbol in the following). Use the ¶ option of your text editor to check for tab stops (→). The read-out cannot handle spaces instead of tab stops and will fail!
- Please note, that the input data format is slightly different than for the settings file!

The first block of the input data is typically for general information about the data, like Date, name of the spectrometer or the measured data and (historically) about the model. At the moment, this is mostly for user readability and not read by the App. It might look like this:

```
[General]
Date: → 29/08/2025
Type: → Nonlinearity
Spectrometer: → COMPANY-MODEL
SN: → 1234
Comment1: → Using measurement procedure ABC.
Comment2: → NL Correction factor = 1 / Nonlinearity
```

This is followed by the data. It is denoted by [DataBlock1] or [MatrixBlock1] (with ascending numbers). The MatrixBlock Option is currently only used for the straylight matrix. Before the actual data there are additional descriptions. For this, use the keyword *Label1* and *Unit1*. Again, use tab stops. After the description, place your data. Denote the start of the data with *DataBegin* and the end of the data with *DataEnd*. This might look like this.

```
[DataBlock1]
Label1: → polynomial coefficients
Unit1: → 1/counts^i
Label2: → polynomial coefficients uncertainty
Unit2: → 1/counts^i

DataBegin
1.00398536260998 → 7.94876996105106E-5
-7.12593090773375E-8 → 9.97818033770663E-9
-3.07851312824383E-12 → 2.29772258847886E-13
DataEnd

[DataBlock2]
Label1: → correlation coefficients
Unit1: → 1

DataBegin
1
-0.887038403431447
0.805077091775988
-0.887038403431447
1
-0.977930432790052
0.805077091775988
-0.977930432790052
1
DataEnd
```

For the bandwidth model using Triangular approach, only two data points are required, the bandwidth and the resolution. This can be implemented using *specific* keywords. Refer to example data, where this is possible. Example:

```
[DataBlock1]
Bandwidth: → 10
Bandwidth unit: px/nm
Pixel Spacing: → 2.5
Pixel Spacing unit: px/nm
```

5. Input data: Preparation of the settings file

5.1. The different sections

The settings file contains sections marked by square brackets. Each section contains different options defined with key-value pairs, where the value is given after the equal sign (e.g. key = value). The sections are separated into the applied corrections, e.g. [Linearity] or [Bandwidth]. An exemplary screenshot of a setting file is given in Figure 9.

Typically, for each section, the first option refers to the model that will be used within this step. Each model then might have further options, that will be defined later in this section.

Applied corrections can be disabled by choosing value "None" for the modelling option. The order of the applied corrections is defined in the source code and is not affected by the order of the sections in the setting file.

The following sections have to be defined:

- General
- Linearity
- Straylight
- Bandwidth
- Distance
- XY-Displacement
- Tilt of Detector
- Pixel to Wavelength
- SR¹
- Interpolation Model

Please note that the name of the sections and options have to be written correctly.

```
[General]
# In this section the Model is defined which will be used for analysis
# You can add additional data of your setup, spectrometer, etc. although it is currently not read by the App and is just for user information purposes
Model = Newstand3
Spectrometer name = Synthetic3
Serial number = Synthetic3_xxx_xxx

[Linearity]
# Choose linearity correction using single polynomial (SinglePol) or multiple polynomials (MultiPol)
Linearity Model = SinglePol
File = Synthetic3_linearitytime.txt

[Straylight]
# Choose straylight correction using matrix method (Matrix)and longpass filter method (LPP)
Straylight Model = Matrix
File = Synthetic3_straylightmatrix.txt

[Bandwidth]
# Choose bandwidth correction using the Woolliams method (BwWoolliams) or Schinke/triangular method (BwTriangular)
Bandwidth Model = BwTriangular
File = Synthetic3_bandwidth.txt

[Distance]
# Consider distance measurement uncertainty of the lamp and detector
# A point light source is assumed.
# Use yes or no for "include distance MU" key if distance MU should be considered
Include distance MU = yes
Distance lamp detector = 300
Distance measurement uncertainty = 1

[XY-Displacement]
# Consider inhomogeneities of the light field on the detector or displacement of the detector in xy direction
# Use min and max value of the light field screening in the detector plane
# Use yes or no for "include XY displacement" key if xy displacement should be considered
Include XY displacement = yes
Min_of_lightfield = 0.9
Max_of_lightfield = 1.1

[Tilt of Detector]
# Consider a possible tilt of the detector to the measurement plane
# Choose whether tilt angle unit is in "radian" or "degree"
# Use yes or no for "include Tilt" key if tilt should be corrected
Include Tilt = yes
Tilt angle unit = radian
Tilt angle = 0.01

[Pixel to Wavelength]
# Choose pixel to wavelength assignment using one polynom(SinglePol), multiple polynomials (MultiPol) or emission line model (EmissionLineModel) for the pixel to wavelength assignment
Pxtowl Model = SinglePol
File = Synthetic3_pxtowavelength.txt

[SR_calibrationchain]
# Choose the correct SR settings according to the model
# For Newstand1 set the section as <SR_singlefile> and add the option <File> with the name of the corresponding .txt file
# For <Newstand2> set the section as <SR_mcfiles> and add the option <spectralresponsivity_mc_data_path> with name of the corresponding zip file
# For <Newstand3> set the section as <SR_calibrationchain>
# Two options <Calchain_light_file> and <Calchain_dark_file> with the names of the files of the corresponding calibration data
# and <spectralresponsivity_mc_data_path> with a Zip file containing the spectral irradiance corresponding to the calibration data file
calchain_light_file = Synthetic3_cal_lightdata.txt
```

Figure 9. Screenshot of the INI settings file that defines the modelling for each spectroradiometer.

¹ The name for the Spectral Responsivity section depends on the applied model and needs to be changed accordingly.

5.2. Available corrections and corresponding models

There are different approaches available on how to physically model the corrections. The NEWSTAND App has at least two different approaches for most of the corrections. The available models are described briefly in the next paragraphs. Appropriate uncertainties need to be defined for the uncertainty analysis using Monte Carlo simulations.

In the following, a short description of each section is given.

5.2.1. General

In the [General] - section the Model is defined which will be used for analysis (key: “**Model**”). Options for values are “**Newstand1**”, “**Newstand2**”, “**Newstand3**” and “**Newstand4**”.

It is possible to add additional meta data of your setup, spectrometer, etc. although it is currently not read by the NEWSTAND App and is just for user information purposes.

5.2.2. Linearity

Apply non-linearities of the detector signal. Select the model via the key “**Linearity_Model**”:

- Value “**SinglePol**”: The detector linearity is corrected using a single n^{th} order polynomial. The correlation of the coefficients is defined by correlation matrices. The random values during Monte Carlo are drawn from uniform distributions.
- Value “**MultiPol**”: Correct linearity using a set of n -distinct 2^{nd} order polynomials.

Use value “**None**” to switch off linearity correction.

The key “**File**” is the name of the file which contains the coefficients. A detailed description of this file is given in section 7.1.

5.2.3. Straylight

Consider internal straylight in the spectroradiometer. Two models are available via the key “**Straylight_Model**”:

- **Matrix**: The straylight is corrected using a Zong straylight matrix [Zong 2006]. The Zong matrix uses one uncertainty value for the whole matrix. This is an assumption but fully appropriate for the needed purpose of evaluation the further uncertainties. For each Monte Carlo run, one random value is drawn from a normal distribution. Thus, the measurement uncertainty contribution is fully wavelength-correlated.
- **LPF**: Straylight is corrected using the long-pass filter method by Ma *et al*, “Uncertainty analysis for RadCalNet instrumented test sites using the Baotou sites BTCN and BSCN as examples,” Remote Sensing, 12, 1696, 2020. The uncertainty of the stray light factors that are used to correct spectral stray light is expressed by one value for the spectral range corresponding to STF derived from the characterisations using one long-pass filter.

Use value “**None**” to switch off straylight correction.

The key “**File**” is the name of the file which contains the matrix or the LPF data. A detailed description of this file is given in section 7.2.

5.2.4. Distance

Includes the uncertainty of the measured distance from lamp to detector in the Monte Carlo analysis. A point light source is assumed.

Activate/deactivate this measurement uncertainty contribution with the key “**Include distance MU**” and the values “**yes**” or “**no**”. The distance of the lamp to the detector has to be provided via key “**Distance lamp detector**” and the distance measurement uncertainty via the key “**Distance measurement uncertainty**”.

For each Monte Carlo run, one random value is drawn. Thus, the measurement uncertainty contribution is fully wavelength-correlated.

5.2.5. XY-Displacement

Considers inhomogeneities of the light field on the detector or displacement of the detector in xy direction. The minimum and the maximum of the light field screening in the detector plane are used as parameters (keys: “**Min_of_lightfield**” and “**Max_of_lightfield**”).

Activate/deactivate this measurement uncertainty contribution with the key “**Include XY displacement**” and the values “**yes**” or “**no**”.

For each Monte Carlo run, one random value is drawn from a uniform distribution in-between these two values. Thus, the measurement uncertainty contribution is fully wavelength-correlated.

5.2.6. Tilt of detector

Consider a possible tilt of the detector to the measurement plane. Tilt is defined via the key “**Tilt angle**” which is given in radian or degree, as defined by the key “**Tilt angle unit**” which can be “radian” or “degree”.

Activate/deactivate this measurement uncertainty contribution with the key “**Include Tilt**” and the values “**yes**” or “**no**”.

For each Monte Carlo run, one random value is drawn from a uniform distribution with half-width of “tilt angle unit”. Thus, the measurement uncertainty contribution is fully wavelength-correlated.

5.2.7. Bandwidth

Applies bandwidth correction. Two models are available via the key “**Bandwidth_Model**”:

- Value “**BwWoolliams**”: The first model uses the Woolliams correction with a linear correction around each pixel [Woolliams 2011]. The uncertainty of the coefficients for the linear corrections is defined as standard deviation. No correlation is considered during Monte Carlo analysis, drawing a new random for each coefficient using a normal distribution with the width of the standard deviation around the mean value.
- Value “**BwTriangular**”: The second model uses a triangular correction with a defined bandwidth and pixel spacing. Full correlation is considered during Monte Carlo analysis drawing only one random value for the whole spectrum using a triangular distribution around the mean value.

Use value “**None**” to switch off bandwidth correction.

The key “**File**” is the name of the file which contains the characterization data. A detailed description of this file is given in section 7.3.

5.2.8. Pixel to Wavelength

The pixel to wavelength assignment can be done in different ways:

- **SinglePol**: Uses a single polynomial of n^{th} order with standard deviations and correlation coefficients.
- **MultiPol**: Experimental model using a 4^{th} order polynomial with additional transfer functions and correlation matrices.
- **EmissionLineModel**: Direct analysis of emission lines in comparison to literature values. Uses type-A measurement uncertainty for the literature data.

The key “**File**” is the name of the file which contains the characterization data. A detailed description of this file is given in section 7.4.

5.2.9. SR_singlefile, SR_mcfiles and SR_calibrationchain

The spectral responsivity is applied differently depending on the used model.

For Newstand1-model use section **[SR_singlefile]** and add the key **File** with the name of the corresponding data file.

For Newstand2-model use section **[SR_mcfiles]** and add the key **“spectralresponsivity_mc_data_path”** with name of the corresponding zip file.

For Newstand3-model use section **[SR_calibrationchain]**. Here, three keys have to be defined:

- Key **“Calchain_light_file”** and key **“Calchain_dark_file”** with the names of the files of the corresponding calibration data.
- Key **“spectralresponsivity_mc_data_path”** with a zip file containing the spectral irradiance corresponding to the calibration data file.

The required characterization data is explained in more detail in section 7.5.

5.2.10. Interpolation Model

Interpolates the resulting spectral irradiance to pre-defined wavelength values. You need to specify if you want to use the interpolation via the key **“Interpolation”** and the values **“yes”** or **“no”**. Define the wavelength interval via the keys **“x_start”**, **“x_stop”** and **“x_delta”**.

The measurement uncertainty in wavelength is transferred by the interpolation to a measurement uncertainty in spectral irradiance.

6. Input data: Preparation of measurement data

Measurement data includes the raw data of the light and dark measurement and is typically given in two lists as (pixel, counts).

There are several examples provided with the NEWSTAND App that can be used as guidelines for users to create their own files. It is recommended to use one of these examples as a starting point for your data.

The measured signal in the presence of light. The Monte Carlo Analysis considers uncorrelated signals and a normal distribution of the standard deviation around the mean value for random value generation.

Measured signal in the absence of light. The light signal is corrected by subtraction of the dark signal. The Monte Carlo Analysis considers uncorrelated signals and a normal distribution of the standard deviation around the mean value for random value generation.

6.1. The light data file

The light data file contains the measured detector counts for each pixel and the standard deviation of the digital signal.

Two keywords are necessary: *Integration time* and *Data time normalized*. Define here the integration time (in seconds) used for measurement and if the given data is already normalized to that in the *[General]* section.

Three columns in the first *DataBlock1* contain the pixel number, the digital signal and the uncertainty of the signal, in this order.

The file should look like this:

```
[General]
Integration time: → 1.0 → s
Data time normalized: → yes

[DataBlock1]
Label1: → Pixelnumber
Unit1: → -
Label2: → Mean of digital signal
Unit2: → counts/s
Label3: → Type A standard uncertainty of the mean
Unit3: → counts/s

DataBegin
1 → 19.80711 → 0.21768
2 → 19.77314 → 0.33710
3 → 20.31451 → 0.28054
...
...
...
2047 → 1521.96225 → 0.37316
2048 → 1156.61306 → 0.23614
DataEnd
```

6.2. The dark data file

The dark data file contains the measured detector counts for each pixel and the standard deviation of the digital signal.

Two keywords are necessary: *Integration time* and *Data time normalized*. Define here the integration time used for measurement and if the given data is already normalized to that in the *[General]* section.

Three columns in the first *DataBlock1* contain the pixel number, the digital signal and the uncertainty of the signal, in this order.

The file should look like this:

```
[General]
Integration time: → 1.0 → s
Data time normalized: → yes

[DataBlock1]
Label1: → Pixelnumber
Unit1: → -
Label2: → Mean of digital signal (dark)
Unit2: → counts/s
Label3: → Type A standard uncertainty of the mean
Unit3: → counts/s

DataBegin
1           →           19.98546           →           0.0200
2           →           19.97104           →           0.04080
3           →           20.01897           →           0.03197
...
...
...
2047        →           1521.96225        →           0.37316
2048        →           1156.61306        →           0.23614
DataEnd
```

7. Input data: Preparation of characterization data

7.1. Linearity file

A polynomial is defined transforming each signal x of the spectrum to correct for linearity in time. The correction is defined as $x_{\text{corr}} = x/p(x)$ with $p(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$. Before the correction is applied, the data is multiplied by the integration time defined in the measurements file header to convert the input from count/s to counts. After correcting for the linearity, the data is time normalized again to output in counts/s.

7.1.1. File when using single polynomial

A single polynomial transforms the spectrum to correct for linearity in time. The same polynomial is used for all integration times. It can be of arbitrary n^{th} order. The order is defined by the number of coefficients given in the first *DataBlock*. The coefficients are stored in ascending number starting with a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n . Each coefficient has an uncertainty that is given in a second column in the first *DataBlock*. The correlation coefficients defining the correlation between the polynomial coefficients are given in the second *DataBlock*.

The file should look like this.

```
[DataBlock1]
Label1: → polynomial coefficients
Unit1: → 1/counts^i
Label2: → polynomial coefficients uncertainty
Unit2: → 1/counts^i

DataBegin
0.99926333 → 0.0
0.00000038 → 0.0
DataEnd

[DataBlock2]
Label1: → correlation coefficients
Unit1: → 1

DataBegin
1.000000
-0.956831
-0.956831
1.000000
DataEnd
```

7.1.2. File when using multiple polynomials

There are different polynomials of 2nd order defined. The coefficients of the polynomials are time dependent. They are defined in the first *DataBlock*. 5 columns are required. The first column defines the number of the polynomial. The second column defines the integration time corresponding the polynomial. It is given in microseconds! The code search for the polynomial with the integration time closest to the actual integration time. The polynomial coefficients are given in the third, fourth and fifth column.

An extra *DataBlock* needs to be defined for each polynomial where the covariance matrix defining the uncertainty and correlation of the coefficients is defined.

The file should look like this:

```
[DataBlock1]
Label1: → polynomial
Label2: → integration time
Unit2: → μs
Label3: → a0
Unit3: → 1
```

```

Label4: → a1
Unit4: → 1/counts
Label5: → a2
Unit5: → 1/counts^2

DataBegin
1 → 2000 → 1.000167E+00 → 1.060052E-08 → -3.675433E-12
2 → 100000 → 9.979840E-01 → -5.549457E-08 → -1.806743E-12
3 → 200000 → 1.000493E+00 → -8.535310E-08 → -2.701769E-12
4 → 64000000 → 9.911227E-01 → -8.455373E-08 → -2.676466E-12
DataEnd

[DataBlock2]
Label1: → -
Label2: → -
Label3: → -

DataBegin
3.318430E-06 → 0.000000E+00 → 0.000000E+00
0.000000E+00 → 4.027693E-14 → -9.781038E-19
0.000000E+00 → -9.781038E-19 → 2.519777E-23
DataEnd

...
...
...

[DataBlock5]
Label1: → -
Label2: → -
Label3: → -

DataBegin
2.310967E-05 → -1.691181E-09 → 2.618522E-14
-1.691181E-09 → 1.600557E-13 → -2.773530E-18
2.618522E-14 → -2.773530E-18 → 5.128221E-23
DataEnd

```

7.2. Stray light file

The stray light correction in the software can be done using a stray light correction matrix by Zong *et al* or a long pass filter method based on stray light factors derived from the characterizations using a broadband source and long pass filters according to the method of Ma *et al*, “Uncertainty analysis for RadCalNet instrumented test sites using the Baotou sites BTCN and BSCN as examples,” Remote Sensing,12,1696, 2020.

7.2.1. File for Zong Matrix

The file uses the tag *Measurement Uncertainty* in the *[General]* section. The stray light matrix of size $n \times n$ with n the number of pixels is set in the *MatrixBlock*.

The file should look like this:

```

[General]
Measurement Uncertainty: → 1.0E-7

[MatrixBlock1]
MatrixBegin
1.000000 → 0.000000 → 0.000000 ...
0.000000 → 1.000000 → 0.000000 ...
0.000000 → 0.000000 → 1.000000 ...

```

```
...  
...  
MatrixEnd
```

7.2.2. Long pass filter method

The file for stray light correction of array spectroradiometer data in UV and short-VIS spectral ranges using stray light factors (STF) contains a *[General]* and a *[StrayLightFactor]* section.

The *[General]* section contains the description of the straylight-sections which are derived from the cut-on pixels corresponding to each cut-on wavelength of the long pass filters used for the characterization of the spectroradiometer to derive the respective STF. In the provided example, 11 long pass filters were used for the characterization measurements yielding respective STFs. Each section contains five numbers:

- sec_begin: pixel-number where the section begins,
- sec_end: pixel-number where the section ends,
- sum_begin: start pixel-number for the sum in the equation,
- sum_end: pixel-number for the sum in the equation, and
- STF(u): measurement uncertainty (k=1) for the STF.

```
[General]  
Date: → today  
  
STFSectionsNum: → 11  
STFSection1: → 1 - 23; 24 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection2: → 24 - 68; 69 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection3: → 69 - 88; 89 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection4: → 89 - 224; 225 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection5: → 225 - 395; 396 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection6: → 396 - 509; 510 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection7: → 510 - 614; 615 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection8: → 615 - 777; 778 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection9: → 778 - 1016; 1017 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection10: → 1017 - 1148; 1149 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
STFSection11: → 1149 - 2048; 1 - 2048; 5.1e-06  
  
[StrayLightFactor]  
Label1: → Pixelnumber  
Label2: → STF  
  
DataBegin  
1 → 2.07E-06  
2 → 1.43E-06  
3 → 2.84E-06  
.....  
2047 → 1.01E-06  
2048 → 1.01E-06  
DataEnd
```

7.3. Bandwidth File

The bandwidth correction can be done using a triangular approximation for the bandpass function as defined by Schinke et al. or using Woolliams generalized approach for bandpass correction using 5 coefficients connecting the counts at pixel i with the 4 pixels equispaced by d pixels around it.

7.3.1. File using triangular approach

For the bandwidth model using Triangular approach, only two data points are required, the bandwidth and the resolution. The necessary keywords are *Bandwidth* and *Pixel Spacing*.

```
[DataBlock1]
Bandwidth: → 10
Bandwidth unit: px/nm
Pixel Spacing: → 2.5
Pixel Spacing unit: px/nm
```

7.3.2. File using Woolliams approach

For the bandwidth model using the Woolliams method [Woolliams 2011] the formula to correct for the bandwidth of the detector at pixel i is defined as

$$x_{\text{corr}}(i) = x(i - 2d) * a_{m2}(i) + x(i - d) * a_{m1}(i) + x(i) * a_0 + x(i + d) * a_{p1} + x(i + 2d) * a_{p2},$$

with pixel distance d . You can set the pixel distance d as a tag in the general section. If no tag is used a default value of $d = 10$ pixels is assumed.

Two *DataBlocks* are required. In the first *DataBlock*, the coefficients a_y are defined depending on the pixel range where they are applied. The first column defines the pixel values in which the coefficients are valid. The code searches for each pixel which of the given pixels is closest and uses the corresponding coefficients. The pixel spacing and number of pixels can be chosen arbitrarily. Columns 2-6 contain the coefficients.

The second *DataBlock* has the same design as the first one but contains the standard deviation of the coefficients.

The file should look like this:

```
[General]
Number of bandwidth correction functions: 3
Pixel distance: 1

[DataBlock1]
Label1: → pixel
Unit1: → counts
Label2: → am2
Unit2: → 1
Label3: → am1
Unit3: → 1
Label4: → a0
Unit4: → 1
Label5: → ap1
Unit5: → 1
Label6: → ap2
Unit6: → 1

DataBegin
1 → 1.403063E-3 → -1.732773E-2 → 1.027144E+0 → -1.165527E-2 → 4.357184E-4
1024 → 6.427448E-4 → -1.278842E-2 → 1.024555E+0 → -1.345474E-2 → 1.045329E-3
2048 → 1.196993E-1 → -8.475675E-1 → 2.381754E+0 → -7.498032E-1 → 9.591761E-2
DataEnd

[DataBlock2]
Label1: → pixel
Label2: → stdv(am2)
Label3: → stdv(am1)
Label4: → stdv(a0)
Label5: → stdv(ap1)
Label6: → stdv(ap2)

DataBegin
1 → 7.670185E-6 → 5.739890E-5 → 2.048731E-5 → 5.925850E-5 → 7.886898E-6
1024 → 2.743324E-5 → 2.777896E-4 → 1.706205E-4 → 1.043417E-4 → 1.631251E-5
```

```
2048 → 8.837752E-4 → 2.780959E-3 → 1.593876E-3 → 4.498029E-3 → 1.187868E-3
DataEnd
```

7.4. Pixel to Wavelength

The pixel to wavelength assignment can be done either by using a single polynomial or by giving emission lines. There is an option to use an experimental model using multiple polynomials.

7.4.1. File using single polynomial for Pixel to Wavelength assignment

The file contains the coefficients for the polynomial converting the pixel values to wavelength values. The polynomial can be of arbitrary n^{th} order which is defined by the length of the coefficient list given in the first *DataBlock*, $\lambda = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$. The coefficients a_i and their uncertainty are defined in the first *DataBlock*. The second *DataBlock* contains the correlation coefficients defining the correlation between each polynomial coefficient.

The file should look like this:

```
[DataBlock1]
Label1: → polynomial coefficients
Unit1: → nm / pixel^i
Label2: → polynomial coefficients uncertainty
Unit2: → nm / pixel^i

DataBegin
248.29420540  0.0
0.41980881   0.0
DataEnd

[DataBlock2]
Label1: → correlation coefficients
Unit1: → 1

DataBegin
1.000000
-0.987920
-0.987920
1.000000
DataEnd
```

7.4.2. File using emission lines for Pixel to Wavelength assignment

The file should look like this:

```
[General]
Date: → today

[Measurement]
Label1: → Reference wavelength → [nm]
Label2: → U(Reference wavelength → [nm]
Label3: → Pixel centroid position → [px]
Label4: → std(Pixel centroid position) → [px]
Label5: → Emission lamp used

DataBegin
253.65171220  0.00022000  17.94872704  2.53107254  Hg
365.33765170  0.00020000  279.87355497  2.53585660  Hg
```

```

435.82011670 0.00014000 448.92026505 2.53616365 Hg
587.56785330 0.00100000 813.93849260 2.53603447 He
706.72330300 0.00141000 1100.92045689 2.53626095 Ar
876.14121000 0.00008000 1508.90006173 2.53571143 Cs
1002.43552000 0.00010000 1812.89770159 2.53571610 Cs
DataEnd

```

7.4.3. File using multiple polynomials for Pixel to Wavelength assignment

This method uses several polynomials and transfer functions depending on the wavelength range for the pixel to wavelength assignment. The method is currently only in an experimental state and uses fixed wavelength ranges and function.

```

0 <= x < 153
153 <= x < 163 p2
163 <= x < 175 p2*(1-f1) + p3*f1
175 <= x < 1425 p3
1425 <= x < 1533 p3*(1-f2) + p4*f2
1533 <= x <=2047 p4

```

7.5. Spectral Responsivity files

Depending on the model, different files for the spectral responsivity are required

7.5.1. File for SR of Model 1

Here, only a best estimate of the SR is multiplied with digital signal. Four columns need to be defined. The first two contain the wavelength and corresponding uncertainty, the third and fourth contain the spectral responsivity and its uncertainty.

File should look like this:

```

[Data]
Label1: → Wavelength
Unit1: → nm
Label2: → Wavelength Uncertainty
Unit2: → nm
Label3: → Spectral responsivity
Unit3: → (W/m^2)/(counts/s)
Label4: → Spectral responsivity Uncertainty
Unit4: → (W/m^2)/(counts/s)

DataBegin
300.00000000 → 0.0 → 1.00000000 → 0.01414214
301.00000000 → 0.0 → 1.00000000 → 0.01414214
302.00000000 → 0.0 → 1.00000000 → 0.01414214
303.00000000 → 0.0 → 1.00000000 → 0.01414214
...
...
1099.00000000 → 0.0 → 1.00000000 → 0.01414214
1100.00000000 → 0.0 → 1.00000000 → 0.01414214
DataEnd

```

7.5.2. Files for SR of Model 2

In Model 2, the SR data is provided as a Monte Carlo data set allowing to model wavelength correlations. The data set should contain several data files (more than 100) in which a simulated SR is saved. In these files, only the raw data is saved with the first column containing the wavelength and the second column containing the SR which results in files like this:

```
300.00000000 → 0.99656454
301.00000000 → 0.99819217
302.00000000 → 1.00003625
...
...
1099.00000000 → 0.99685756
1100.00000000 → 0.99483434
```

No additional information or keywords should be given. Each file can only contain one SR. Thus, several files are necessary.

Compress all files into a zip-file. This zip file is unpacked temporarily during the data processing.

7.5.3. SR files for SR of Model 3

Similar to model 2 but SR is calculated separately during each Monte Carlo run using the measured raw data of the calibration ("calibration chain"). Due to the usage of two data chains, calibration and measurements are modelled in a consistent manner.

A similar files structure to the files for Model 2 is necessary. But, the files contain the reference spectrum used to calculate the SR instead of the SR. The Data format is the same as for Model 2. Two columns contain wavelength and reference spectrum. No additional information should be given. Each file only contains one reference spectrum. Thus, several files are necessary.

Compress all files into a zip file.

8. Getting Started - Best Practices

The following best practices can help improve data processing, allow an easier start and usage of the software.

- Do not start all data files from scratch. We recommend, copy first one of the examples provided and run it successfully within the NEWSTAND App. Add your data step-by-step.
- Make sure that the data (vectors) being combined directly are the same size. For example, light and dark data must be the same size.
- It is recommended to use UTF-8 encoding for all data files.
- Format all data files carefully, readout is strict.
- Be aware of the error messages on the right side in the software GUI. They might seem to be a bit cryptic in the beginning but usually give good hints where the error occurred.
- Go visually through all data processing steps (by clicking on the corresponding step in the list) and check whether the correction is correctly applied.
- Be careful with wavelength-correlations especially when integrating over the resulting spectral irradiances. For integral values, the correlations have to be considered carefully.
- Start with a measurement where you know the result. This allows you to check if everything is properly set up.

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